

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Beyond Beauty: Exploring the Impact of Cosmeceuticals on Early Skin Aging

Gayatri Yeole*, Ajay Baitule, Himani Malode, Jaydeep Wankhade

Vidyabharti College of Pharmacy, C K Naidu Road, Amravati

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 22 May, 2025

Keywords:

Aging, Early aging, Genetic factors, Prevention of aging, Anti-aging agents, Premature aging

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15490334

ABSTRACT

Aging, particularly early or premature aging, is influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. Early skin aging results from changes in the skin's structure, including collagen and elastin degradation, free radical damage, and hormonal shifts. Environmental elements such as excessive sunlight, poor nutrition, lack of sleep, and smoking accelerate this process. The biological age of the skin can be evaluated by its thickness, elasticity, and moisture levels. Cosmeceuticals, including peptides, vitamins, botanicals, and hydroxy acids, play a significant role in the prevention and treatment of premature aging. These agents help restore collagen synthesis, improve hydration, and provide protection against environmental stressors. By using moisturizers, sunscreens, antioxidants, and retinoids, skin aging can be mitigated. This paper explores the underlying mechanisms of early aging and the potential of Cosmeceuticals in slowing down this process.

INTRODUCTION

Skin aging is a complex biological process that affects multiple layers of the skin, including the epidermis, dermis, and the dermo-epidermal junction. Over time, intrinsic factors such as genetics and hormonal changes, as well as extrinsic factors like UV exposure, pollution, and lifestyle choices, lead to structural and functional changes in the skin. These changes manifest as

wrinkles, loss of elasticity, uneven pigmentation, and an overall decline in skin barrier function. Aging of the skin also reduces its ability to repair itself, regulate temperature, and provide immune protection, contributing to visible signs of aging and compromised skin health. Premature or early aging occurs when these processes are accelerated by external factors, such as excessive sun exposure, pollution, poor nutrition, and insufficient sleep. As skin aging progresses, there is a decline in the production of key components

*Corresponding Author: Gayatri Yeole

Address: Vidyabharti College of Pharmacy, C K Naidu Road, Amravati

Email ✉: gayatriyeole19@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

like collagen and elastin, resulting in the weakening of the extracellular matrix, thinning of the skin, and increased vulnerability to environmental damage. Understanding these underlying mechanisms is crucial for developing effective prevention strategies. Cosmeceuticals, a category of skincare products that combine cosmetic and therapeutic benefits, have emerged as a promising solution to combat premature aging. These products incorporate bioactive ingredients such as peptides, vitamins, antioxidants, and botanical extracts to enhance skin repair, improve hydration, stimulate collagen synthesis, and protect against environmental aggressors. This review explores the causes of early aging, the science behind the aging process, and the role of Cosmeceuticals in preventing and mitigating its effects.

Skin Aging

Skin aging takes place on different levels in the epidermis, dermis and in the dermo-epidermal junction. The skin provides barrier function, wound healing, thermoregulation, sensory function, immune function and vitamin D metabolism, which decline globally with increased age. [1] Alterations in skin structure result in laxity, wrinkles, slackness and neoplasms of the skin. [2] Structural stability of the epidermis, dermis and hypodermis depends on the integrity of extracellular matrix such as collagen and elastin, a stable cellular proliferation process, intact vascularization and sufficient barrier function with lipids and skin hydration.[3] The biological age of the skin can be analysed by the structure of the skin including thickness, collagen matrix, cell size, as well as a functional analysis with elasticity, torsion extensibility, neuroperception, trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL) and proliferation rate measurements. [4] Extracellular matrix components Collagen is a major component of the

extracellular matrix and contributes to the structural stability of the skin.[5] The different types of collagens fulfil different functions: collagen VII is a component of anchoring fibrils and stabilizes the dermal-epidermal adhesion, while collagen XVII exists in hemidesmosomes, and the extracellular matrix in the dermis contains collagen type I and III in a ratio that changes with ageing.[6] Due to declining numbers of fibroblasts with increasing age, collagen and elastin synthesis are subsequently reduced, and collagen fibres are thinner with reduced density.[7,8] Moreover, collagen and elastic fibre degradation is increased by activation of metalloproteinases (MMPs) through UV radiation and smoking, and calcifications stimulate elastin fibre degeneration.[9,10] Degenerated collagen fibres lose their crosslinking formation which stabilizes the skin structure and accumulates in unorganized bundles, and degenerated collagen subsequently appears basophilic.[11] Due to molecular structural changes of collagen, its integrity and function are impaired, and the strength and resistance of skin are reduced. Vitamin A and moisture have been shown to reduce collagen damage. [12]

Photoageing

Photoageing interacts with the physiological ageing process and accelerates ageing. However, the mechanism of ageing acceleration through UV radiation has yet to be fully elucidated. UVA penetrates the dermis and damages both the epidermis and dermis, whereas UVB radiation is predominantly epidermally absorbed. UV radiation damages the DNA in keratinocytes and melanocytes and induces production of the soluble epidermal factor (ESF) and proteolytic enzymes. UVB activates MMPs and induces thymidine dimers, which cause an accumulation of mutations, and UVA radiation produces ROS [13]

Non-UV-exposed skin shows alterations caused by ageing in the epidermis and the basal cells. [14] UV-exposed skin is thin, finely wrinkled, smooth, dry, sallow and pale, with loss of elasticity. [15] Photoageing of UV-exposed skin depends on the skin type and exhibits different characteristics. [16]

BACKGROUND

a) Genetic alterations

Telomeres are the terminal components of chromosomes. In each cell division cycle, telomeres are shortened until the cell-cycle arrests and apoptosis commences. Throughout the cellular ageing process, an inclination of the DNA repair capacity occurs and is caused by decreased protein levels. [17] Alterations in DNA stability, mitochondrial function, ubiquitin-induced proteolysis, cellular metabolism and an accumulation of gene mutations also contribute to cellular ageing. [18] Gene expression and protein synthesis are the main orchestrators of the ageing process. A combination of processes has been described including the transforming growth factor (TGF) pathway with tumour-suppressor activity, apoptotic genes being upregulated due to the downregulation of FOXO1. Furthermore, cytoskeletal proteins, extracellular matrix components, proteins involved in cell-cycle control, disturbed lipid metabolism, and altered insulin and STAT3 signalling have all been implicated in the genetic ageing process. [19]

b) Reactive oxygen species (ROS) and free radicals

Free radicals are oxygen molecules with an unpaired number of electrons that take electrons from other components. Consequently, these molecules are highly reactive and damage cell structures such as cell membranes and DNA,

resulting in cell death or mutations and cellular ageing. Antioxidants, such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, alpha-tocopherol, ascorbic acid, ubiquinone, and glutathione, protect the genetic material against ROS and occur physiologically in the skin and cellular membranes. UV light can inhibit these antioxidants and cause photochemical reactions. [20] Accordingly, ROS-induced ageing of skin can be mitigated by physical filters, such as microparticles of zinc oxide and titanium oxide, and by supplements with antioxidative abilities, including vitamins A, E and C, coenzyme Q10 and alpha-lipoic acid. [21]

c) Hormones

Hormone synthesis and levels of circulating hormones decline with age, which affects cell metabolism and interacts with gene expression and protein synthesis [22] Sex hormone levels play a key role in the accelerated ageing process, as well as declining levels of melatonin, cortisol, thyroxine, growth hormone, insulin-like growth factor, vitamin D 1–25 dihydroxy and fewer receptors of interleukin and beta adrenalin are involved. Oestrogen is crucial for skin integrity and stimulates DNA repair. Oestrogen therapy stimulates collagen synthesis, slows its degradation and can consequently reduce skin thinning, helping to maintain skin hydration. In the postmenopausal period, topical oestrogens, phytoestrogens or selective oestrogen receptor modulators may contribute to skin health improvement. When considering the general use of oestrogen for improving skin health, however, the appropriate timepoint for the start of a oestrogen therapies needs to be evaluated carefully to mitigate the associated risks and maximize benefits. [23] Knowing the underlying mechanisms of facial and skin aging requires a comprehension of these processes. By examining

fundamental causes and preliminary therapy research, this study expands on current understanding by reviewing the body of research on the aging of the skin, especially that of the face.

CAUSES

a) Early aging caused by free radicals

These are the molecules that are either consumed or produced in the body, with the living cells molecules. The cells of all bodily organs (Heart and arteries) can get damaged due to it that may cause aging. When free radicals enter into the body, Antioxidants like Vitamin C, Vitamin E, zinc and selenium can counterbalance their damaging effects by removing them. [24]

b) Insufficient nutrition

The sufficient nutrients are required for cell functioning, repairing, or reproduction. Every Cell in our body requires oxygen, vitamins, minerals, amino acids, sugar, etc. Aging may be Caused by a lack of a “well-balanced diet” that lacks essential vitamins and minerals.

c) Excessive or insufficient sunlight

The major cause of aging and some Health consequences may be the exposure of either too much sunlight or too little sunlight. Excessive sunlight harms the skin and increases the chance of skin cancer, while insufficient exposure to sunlight results in poor calcium assimilation and failing general health, can lead to severe psychological depression, and possibly contributes to being overweight. [25]

d) Insufficient sleep

Normally the body performs many important restorative activities during sleep. Older people wake up an average of 3 or 4 times each night and

also are more aware of being awake. This happens because they spend less time in deep sleep. A growing body of research indicates that not getting enough sleep may also increase the risk of several conditions and chronic diseases including diabetes, cardiovascular disease, obesity, and depression, nocturia, anxiety and premature aging. [26]

Prevention of Early Aging

To prevent premature skin aging following treatment and protection methods are recommended. It includes:

a) Use of Moisturizers and emollients

Moisturizers can be classified as hydrophilic or lipophilic. Hydrophilic moisturizers are capable of attracting water and are therefore crucial for maintaining the hydration of the skin. In contrast, lipophilic moisturizers tend to remain on the surface of the skin, thereby assisting in the maintenance of the skin barrier.[27]The hydrophilic components of a product are of primary importance for skin hydration, Whereas the lipophilic components serve the dual purpose of remaining on the surface of the skin as a barrier layer, preventing the evaporation of water and assisting in the recovery of the barrier function.[28]moisturizers have been shown to induce the expression of epidermal differentiation markers, such as FLG and loricrin.[29]A moisturizer including urea and glycerol has been demonstrated barrier-strengthening effects, enhanced skin moisturization, and provided protection against irritation.[30]Different types of emollient cream exhibit diverse physiological effects on the skin barrier in adults with atopic dermatitis. Another study has indicated that creams containing glycyrrhetic acid, urea, and glycerol were more effective than their respective controls (vehicle, placebo, or no moisturizer) in

both the participant, and Physician evaluations. [31] Emollients soften the skin and make it smoother. [28] The emollients, including diisopropyl, dilinoleate and isopropyl isostearate, facilitate the formation of a robust protective film on the skin surface. The fattening emollients, comprising castor oil, propylene glycol, jojoba oil, isostearyl isostearate, and octyl stearate, facilitate the formation of a thin layer on the skin surface. This film is slightly greasy and has a longer-Lasting effect. [32]

b) Facial massage

Facial massages can help reduce the appearance of wrinkles by improving blood circulation, increasing collagen production, and promoting cell renewal.

c) Washing your face or using a cleanser to remove makeup.

A cleanser can remove makeup without excessive rubbing without irritating the skin.

d) Skin protection from the sun

We can protect our skin from the excessive exposure from sun radiation by seeking shade, wearing sun-protective clothing which includes a lightweight, long-sleeved shirt, pants, a wide-brimmed hat, and sunglasses with UV protection. Daily application of a broad-spectrum, water-resistant sunscreen with an SPF 30 or higher has been recommended by dermatologists to prevent aging.

e) Avoid scrubbing of skin

Washing your face with chemical face wash should be in limit after sweating. We have to avoid excess scrubbing and use skin care products that are labelled as „hypoallergenic“, „fragrance free“, or „non-comedogenic.“ With repetitive facial

movements, like squinting, frowning should be avoided. By changing over lifestyle and proper care of skin it can protect it from early aging.

f) Avoidance of harmful radiation

The skin should be protected from harmful ultraviolet radiation, be applied to tanner and cover the skin.

g) Addiction

Smoking greatly speeds up skin aging and causes skin wrinkles. Alcohol dehydrates the skin, which causes damage over time.

h) Drinking herbal tea

The antioxidants in green tea and matcha can benefit your skin and body, also a study found that lemon balm leaf extract can make skin more elastic and correct tissue damage.

i) Adaptation of a healthy lifestyle

Eating a healthy, well-balanced diet with plenty of fresh fruits and vegetables may help prevent damage that leads to premature skin aging.

j) Regular exercise

Exercising daily is advised to improve blood circulation and boost the immune system. It makes the skin more youthful and healthier.

k) Enough sleep

During sleeping posture, usually in a lay down position, the cardiovascular system can relax, and the spine can recharge. It provides energy to cells to rebuild and repair that promotes cell growth.

l) Retinol cream

It is a skin care product, derivative of vitamin A and recommended at doses of up to 2%. Daily application can help prevent premature skin aging. [33,34]

m) Metformin

It is used as anti-diabetic drug and found its efficacy as an anti-aging agent. It controls hyperglycaemia and hyperinsulinemia factors of aging through regulation of SIRT1 activity. The cellular metabolic mechanism is regulated by metformin during the period of stress. It synchronizes among several different age-related transcription factor pathways resulting in cell survival. [35]

COSMECEUTICALS

a) Peptides

The role of peptides In Cosmeceuticals revolves around the hypothesis that peptide fragments of collagen and elastin can act as positive feedback signals for their own continued synthesis. Peptides of interest include pal-KTTKS (Matrixyl), Ac-EEMQRR (Argireline), and Cu- GHK. The peptide pal-KTTKS is a fragment of dermal collagen that stimulates new collagen synthesis in vitro and is postulated to facilitate wound healing. [36]It has high potency and was shown to improve wrinkled skin when applied topically at very low doses and with minimal skin irritation. Cu-GHK is also a fragment of dermal collagen, and the copper moiety is a necessary cofactor for collagen synthesis. Many peptides, such as Ac-EEMQRR, mimic botulinum toxin and function to cause muscle relaxation by inhibiting neurotransmitter release. [36,37] Peptides are short chains composed of 2 to 50 amino acids linked by peptide bonds. Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins, and when they are connected in chains, they form peptides. Among major bioactive

compounds, peptides have attracted scientific attention due to their ideal functional roles as regulators/signaling molecules for homeostasis, stress, immunity, defense, growth, and reproduction. They also possess strengths such as high safety, low irritation, and cost-effective production. These peptides are derived from various natural sources, including plants, animals, and microorganisms, and have Demonstrated diverse physiological effects such as antioxidant, anti-aging, moisturizing, collagen-promoting, and wound-healing properties, as evidenced by various in vitro and In vivo studies, and clinical trial results.[36,37] Due to the increasing demand for cosmeceutical products, there is growing interest in the development of next-generation products based on bioactive peptides. Therefore, the safety evaluation of cosmetic peptides, especially from an efficacy perspective, must be seriously considered. It is well known that an effective amount of cosmetic peptides can provide significant positive effects on the skin, while minimizing undesirable effects such as skin toxicity, sensitivity, and irritation. Bioactive peptides are widely used as functional ingredients in dermatology and the cosmetic fields due to their potent single/multi-functional biological properties, such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-aging, and anti-inflammatory activities. These peptides can enhance skin health by improving various aspects including extracellular matrix synthesis, innate immunity, inflammation, and pigmentation disorders. [38,39,40,41] Collagen-promoting, and wound-healing properties, as evidenced by various in vitro and In vivo studies, and clinical trial results.[42]For instance, palmitoyl pentapeptide-3 was one of the first synthetic bioactive peptides, stimulating collagen synthesis for anti-aging and wound-healing treatments.[43]Copper Gly-His-Lys (Cu-GHK) was developed for skin healing, collagen synthesis promotion, and DNA damage repair, and is

included in cosmetics.[44]The tripeptide-copper complex glycyl-L-histidyl-L-lysine-Cu²⁺ stimulates matrix metalloproteinase-2 expression by fibroblast cultures.[45]Acetyl hexapeptide-3 (Argireline) is another popular commercial peptide known for its anti-wrinkle and moisturizing properties.[46] In a previous study, 42 peptides based on the sequence of the skin structural protein Loricrin were identified and synthesized. The elastase inhibitory activity and Skin cell proliferating–promoting efficacy of these tetrapeptides were evaluated. As a result, Tetrapeptide-68 was selected as the final anti-wrinkle peptide due to its elastase inhibitory activity and skin cell proliferating– promoting ability. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of Tetrapeptide-68 (100 ppm) in an O/W formulation for improving periorbital wrinkles in adult women.

b) Vitamins

For the purpose of treating and preventing aging skin, especially photoaging skin, numerous cosmeceutical products are created and promoted. The term “photoaging” describes the harm that long-term exposure to UV radiation from the sun does to the skin over the course of a person’s lifespan. The use of topical antioxidants and substances that aid in DNA repair and collagen synthesis stimulation are potential treatments for skin that has already been harmed, even if wearing UVA and UVB sunscreen every day is the most crucial preventive precaution against photoaged skin. Evidence supports the effectiveness of topical synthetic Vitamin A or retinoids, including tretinoin, adapalene, and tazarotene. There is also a wealth of studies supporting the esthetic benefits of these prescription retinoids. [47] Tretinoin induces production of type I and II procollagen in skin and reduces collagen breakdown by inhibiting metalloproteinases. The overall effect is a thickening of the dermis as the skin is “filled in”

with glycosaminoglycans, helping to reduce fine lines and wrinkles. [48] The vitamin E After years of excessive exposure to free radicals, endogenous Vitamin E depletes, leading to oxidative damage and its function as an epidermal antioxidant by absorbing the sun spectrum of UV rays. So, a lot of research has examined the potential benefits of topical Vitamin E, particularly in alpha-tocopherol, which is its most active form, to prevent sunburn and to improve the wrinkling and hyperpigmentation brought on by free radicals. [49] When applied prior to UV exposure, studies have shown its effectiveness in lowering UV-associated erythema and edema. Furthermore, virtually no negative consequences from using vitamin E topically have been documented. [50] Vitamin B3, sometimes known as nicotinamide or niacinamide, is a recently discovered cosmeceutical. Its important function in antioxidizing processes. When well-tolerated topically, niacinamide has been demonstrated to increase lipids and epidermal protein, minimize water loss from the skin, and strengthen the skin’s defenses against irritation. [51] Niacinamide also reduces facial dyspigmentation via a mechanism that inhibits melanosome transfer from melanocytes to keratinocytes. Topical niacinamide remains one-third to one-fifth as effective as topical 0.025% tretinoin. [52] Vitamin C, also known as L-ascorbic acid, Topical Vitamin C application is a popular as oral supplementation increases concentration minimally. [53] It primarily aids in the manufacture of collagen. Research findings show that topical vitamin C has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities. As a result, 3% ascorbic acid has been shown to minimize face wrinkles and erythema related to postoperative laser resurfacing. [54] Thus, Vitamins value in protection and restoration of skin.

c) Botanicals

Plant-based cosmetic agents are becoming more and more popular in the cosmetic industry. There is a vast array of botanical treatments available, and several claims are made about their benefits for dermatology. Nevertheless, not many studies have been done to support these claims and look at the efficacy and safety of these substances. Ginkgo biloba, silymarin, ginseng, soy, and green tea are among the plant materials that have demonstrated the ability to improve the condition and appearance of skin. Ginkgo biloba is a popular botanical that is included in moisturizers due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities. Extracts from *G. biloba* promote the growth of fibroblasts and the production of collagen. [55] Ginseng is another botanical that has demonstrated significant dermatologic potential when applied topically, with the apparent action of reversing the manifestations of decreased hyaluronan levels that occurs with aging; other *in vitro* studies show that ginseng extracts have the ability to inhibit melanogenesis in melanoma cells, suggesting a possible role as a depigmentation or whitening agent for skin. [56] Numerous dermatological benefits of soy and its isoflavones have been reported; they are attributed, in part, to their antioxidant properties and the metabolites' estrogen-like action. It is believed that it binds to estrogen receptors in the nucleus of cells to exert its phytoestrogen activity, which may prevent the thinning of skin and loss of collagen that happens after menopause. It has been discovered that soy milk and soybean protease inhibitors have the capacity to reverse UV-induced hyperpigmentation and exhibit depigmenting properties. [57] Finally, green tea polyphenols are being heavily promoted for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, which include preventing UV-induced lipid peroxidation *in vitro*.²³ Additionally, research shows that green tea polyphenols boost collagen formation in

human fibroblasts and block the activity of collagenase. [58]

d) Hydroxy Acids

The group of acids called hydroxyacids includes α -, β -, polyhydroxy, and bionic acids. The most popular and widely utilized type of glycolic acid is α -hydroxyacid because of its demonstrated anti-aging properties and capacity to alleviate hyperpigmentation and acne-prone skin. [59] beneficial in the treatment of ichthyosis, verrucous growths, and dry skin. By promoting the manufacture of collagen, glycosaminoglycans, and elastic fibers, hydroxyacid treatment thickens the dermis and reduces wrinkles and fine lines. [60] Gluconolactone is a polyhydroxyacid widely used in skin care products that has been shown *in vitro* to protect against UV radiation by trapping free radicals. [61] The hydroxyacids are frequently employed as peeling agents, particularly lactic and glycolic acids. Hydroxyacid peels are being used more often to speed up exfoliation and promote skin renewal to enhance hyperpigmentation and skin texture. They are applied to the skin in high concentrations for brief periods of time.

e) Growth Factor

Growth factors mediate signaling pathways, especially those connected to wound healing, by acting as regulatory proteins. N-6 furfuryl adenine, or kinetin, is a plant growth factor that has been examined in cultures of human skin fibroblasts. Studies conducted *in vitro* have indicated that the regular application of kinetin may be able to both postpone and lessen the severity of the skin changes that come with aging. Kinetin inhibits the aging-related changes in growth rates and macromolecular synthesis, as well as changes in cell size and shape. By imitating superoxide dismutase, kinetin functions as a scavenger of reactive oxygen species and an inhibitor of the

generation of free radicals. Topical kinetin may help skin texture, reduce hyperpigmentation, and stop trans epidermal water loss, according to other clinical research. [62]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, early skin aging is influenced by various intrinsic and extrinsic factors, including genetic alterations, hormonal imbalances, exposure to UV radiation, oxidative stress, and lifestyle factors such as poor nutrition, lack of sleep, and excessive sunlight exposure. These factors collectively contribute to changes in the structural integrity and function of the skin, leading to visible signs of aging such as wrinkles, laxity, and pigmentation disorders. Preventive measures and therapeutic approaches, including the use of Cosmeceuticals, offer promising interventions to delay or mitigate the effects of premature aging. Cosmeceuticals, particularly those containing peptides, vitamins, botanicals, and growth factors, play a vital role in enhancing skin health by promoting collagen synthesis, protecting against oxidative damage, improving skin hydration, and stimulating skin regeneration. The development of innovative formulations based on bioactive peptides and antioxidants continues to evolve, with ongoing research focusing on maximizing their efficacy while minimizing side effects. A holistic approach to skin care that integrates the use of Cosmeceuticals, sun protection, a balanced diet, regular exercise, and sufficient sleep can effectively slow down the process of premature aging and improve overall skin health. As scientific understanding deepens, cosmeceutical products will likely continue to advance, offering more targeted and potent solutions for maintaining youthful, healthy skin.

REFERENCES

1. Gilchrest BA, Krutmann J. *Skin Aging*. Heidelberg: Springer Science & Business Media; 2006
2. Farage MA, Miller KW, Maibach HI. *Textbook of Aging Skin*. Heidelberg: Springer Science & Business Media; 2009.
3. Braverman IM. Ultrastructure and organization of the cutaneous microvasculature in normal and pathologic states. *J Invest Dermatol*. 1989; 93(2, Supplement): S2–9. doi:10.1038/jid.1989.2
4. Farage MA, Miller KW, Maibach HI. *Textbook of Aging Skin*. Heidelberg: Springer Science & Business Media; 2009.
5. Ricard-Blum S. The collagen family. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol*. 2011; 3(1):a004978. Doi:10.1101/cshperspect.a00498
6. Has C, Kern JS. Collagen XVII. *Dermatol Clin*. 2010; 28(1): 61–6. Doi: 10.1016/j.det.2009.10.007
7. Vitellaro-Zuccarello L. Stereological analysis of collagen and elastic fibers in the normal human dermis: Variability with age, sex, and body region. *The Anatomical Record*. 1994; 238(2): 153– 62.
8. Duncan KO, Leffell DJ. Preoperative assessment of the elderly patient. *Dermatol Clin*. 1997; 15(4): 583–93. Doi:10.1016/S0733-8635(05)70468-X
9. Demierre M-F, Brooks D, Koh HK, Geller AC. Public knowledge, awareness, and perceptions of the association between skin aging and smoking. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 1999; 41(1): 27–30. Doi:10.1016/S0190-9622(99)70401-9
10. Lahmann C, Bergemann J, Harrison G, Young AR. Matrix metalloproteinase-1 and skin ageing in smokers. *Lancet*. 2001; 357(9260): 935–6. Doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(00)04220-3
11. Scharffetter-Kochanek K, Brenneisen P, Wenk J, Herrmann G, Ma W, Kuhr L, et al. Photoaging of the skin from phenotype to

- mechanisms. *Exp Gerontol.* 2000; 35(3): 307–16. Doi:10.1016/S0531-5565(00)00098-X
12. Ricard-Blum S. The collagen family. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol.* 2011; 3(1): a004978. Doi:10.1101/cshperspect.a004978
- Verzár F. The aging of collagen. *Sci Am.* 1963; 208(4): 104–17.
13. Sams WM. Sun-induced aging: clinical and laboratory observations in man. *Dermatol Clin.* 1986; 4(3): 509–16. doi:10.1016/S0733-8635(18)30814-3
14. Makrantonaki E, Zouboulis C. Molecular etiology of skin aging. How important is the genetic make-up? *Der Hautarzt; Zeitschrift für Dermatologie, Venerologie, und verwandte Gebiete.* 2011; 62: 582–7.
15. Makrantonaki E, Zouboulis CC. Characteristics and Pathomechanisms of endogenously aged skin. *DRM.* 2007; 214(4): 352–60. Doi:10.1159/000100890
16. Han A, Chien AL, Kang S. Photoaging. *Dermatol Clin.* 2014; 32(3): 291–9. Doi: 10.1016/j.det.2014.03.015
17. Gilchrist BA, Krutmann J. *Skin Aging. Heidelberg: Springer Science & Business Media; 2006*
18. Makrantonaki E, Zouboulis C. Molecular etiology of skin aging. How important is the genetic make-up? *Der Hautarzt; Zeitschrift für Dermatologie, Venerologie, und verwandte Gebiete.* 2011; 62: 582–7.
19. Welle S, Brooks AI, Delehanty JM, Needler N, Thornton CA. Gene expression profile of aging in human muscle. *Physiol Genom.* 2003; 14(2): 149–59.
20. Fuchs J, Huflejt ME, Rothfuss LM, Wilson DS, Carcamo G, Packer L. Acute effects of near ultraviolet and visible light on the cutaneous antioxidant defense system. *Photochem Photobiol.* 1989; 50(6): 739–44.
21. Pelle E, Muizzuddin N, Mammone T, Marenus K, Maes D. Protection against endogenous and UVB-induced oxidative damage in stratum corneum lipids by an antioxidant-containing cosmetic formulation. *Photodermatol Photoimmunol Photomed.* 1999; 15(3-4): 115–9.
22. Castelo-Branco C, Figueras F, Martínez de Osaba MJ, Arnell JA. Facial wrinkling in postmenopausal women. Effects of smoking status and hormone replacement therapy. *Maturitas.* 1998; 29(1): 75–86. Doi:10.1016/S0378-5122(97)00087-X
23. Shu YY, Maibach HI. Estrogen and Skin. *Am J Clin Dermatol.* 2011; 12(5): 297–311. Doi:10.2165/11589180-000000000-00000
24. Adam SZ, Marie SRS, Helene CFC. Updating the Free Radical Theory of Aging. *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.*, 2020
25. Weyand CM, Goronzy JJ. Aging of the Immune System. Mechanisms and Therapeutic Targets. *Ann Am Thorac Soc.*, 2016; 13(5): S422-S428.
26. Swati Kale, Gita Chaurasia*, Rani Divekar and Arati Kaldoke. Mechanism, process and prevention of early aging.
27. Kelleher MM, Phillips R, Brown SJ, Cro S, Cornelius V, Carlsen KCL, et al. Skin care interventions in infants for preventing eczema and food allergy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2022;11:CD013534.
28. van Zuuren EJ, Fedorowicz Z, Christensen R, Lavrijsen A, Arents BWM. Emollients and moisturisers for Eczema. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2017;2:CD012119
29. Kim BE, Leung DYM. Significance of Skin Barrier Dysfunction in Atopic Dermatitis. *Allergy Asthma Immunol Res.* 2018; 10:207–15.
30. Danby SG, Andrew PV, Taylor RN, Kay LJ, Chittock J, Pinnock A, et al.
31. Van Zuuren EJ, Fedorowicz Z, Arents BWM. Emollients and moisturizers for eczema: abridged Cochrane systematic review

- including GRADE assessments. *Br J Dermatol.* 2017; 177:1256–71
32. Draelos ZD. The science behind skin care: Moisturizers. *J Cosmet Dermatol.* 2018; 17:138–44.
33. Mishra SK, Balendra V, Esposto J, Obaid AA, Maccioni RB, Jha NK, Perry G, Moustafa M, Al-Shehri M, Singh MP, et al. Therapeutic Antiaging Strategies. *Biomedicines*, 2022;10: 2515.33. Christian.
35. Podhorecka M, Ibanez B, Dmoszyńska A. Metformin – its potential anti-cancer and anti-aging effects. *Postepy Hig Med Dosw (Online)*, 2017; 71(0): 170-175.
36. Robinson L, Fitzgerald N, Berge C, et al. Pentapeptide offers improvement in human photo aged facial skin. *Ann Dermatol Venereol.* 2002; 129:1S105.
37. Mas-Chamberlin C, Lintner K, Basset L, et al. Relevance of antiwrinkle treatment of a peptide: 4 months clinical double-blind study vs. excipient. *Ann Dermatol Venereol.* 2002; 129:1S456.
38. Kobayashi, T.; Nagao, K. “Deepening” Insight on Skin Aging and Anti-microbial Immunity. *Cell Metab.* 2019, 29, 515–517.
39. Zou, T.B.; He, T.P.; Li, H.B.; Tang, H.W.; Xia, E.Q. The structure-activity relationship of the antioxidant peptides from natural proteins. *Molecules* 2016, 21, 72.
40. Yu, W.; Field, C.J.; Wu, J. Purification and identification of anti-inflammatory peptides from spent hen muscle proteins hydrolysate. *Food Chem.* 2018, 253, 101–107.
41. Michalak, M.; Pierzak, M.; Kręćisz, B.; Suliga, E. Bioactive compounds for skin health: A review. *Nutrients* 2021, 13, 203.
42. Aguilar-Toalá, J.E.; Hernández-Mendoza, A.; González-Córdova, A.F. Vallejo-Cordoba, B.; Liceaga, A.M. Potential role of natural bioactive peptides for development of cosmeceutical skin products. *Peptides* 2019, 122, 170170.
43. Lima, T.N.; Moraes, C.A.P. Bioactive peptides: Applications and relevance for Cosmeceuticals. *Cosmetics* 2018, 5, 21.
44. Siméon, A.; Emonard, H.; Hornebeck, W.; Maquart, F.X.
45. *Life Sci.* 2000, 67, 2257–2265 Pickart, L.; Schagen, S. New data of the Cosmeceutical and tripeptide GHK. SOFW.
46. Im, A.R.; Nam, J.; Cha, S.; Seo, Y.K.; Chae, S.; Kim, J.Y. Wrinkle reduction using a topical herbal cream in subjects with greater yin (Tae-eumin) type: A randomized double-blind placebo- controlled study. *Eur. J. Integr. Med.* 2018, 20, 173–181.
47. Kang S, Voorhess JJ. Photoaging therapy with topical tretinoin: an evidence-based analysis. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 1998;39:S55–S61.
48. Manela-Azulay M, Bagatin E. Cosmeceutical Vitamins. *Clinics in Dermatology.* 2009; 27:469– 74.
49. Dreher F, Gabard B, Scwindt DA, et al. Topical melatonin in combination with vitamins E and C protects skin from ultraviolet-induced erythema: a human study in vivo. *Br J Dermatol.* 1998; 139:332–9.
50. Thiele JJ, Ekanayake-Mudiyanselage S, Hsieh SN. Cosmeceutical vitamins: vitamin E. In: Draelos ZD, editor. *Cosmeceuticals*. 1st ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders; 2005. Pp. 47–54.
51. Bisset DL, Oblong JE, Saud A, Berge CA, Trejo AV, Biedermann KA. Topical niacinamide provides skin aging appearance benefits while enhancing barrier function. *Journal of Clin Derm.* 2003;31: S9–S18.
52. Bisset DL, Oblong JE, Berge CA. Niacinamide: a B vitamin that improves aging facial skin appearance. *Dermatol Surg.* 2005; 31:860–66.

53. Pinnell SR, Yang HS, Omar M, et al. Topical L-ascorbic acid: percutaneous absorption studies. *Dermatol Surg.* 2001; 27:137–42.
54. Raschke T, Koop U, Dusing HJ, et al. Topical activity of ascorbic acid: from in vitro optimization to in vivo efficacy. *Skin Pharmacol Physiol.* 2004; 17:200–206.
55. Kim SJ, Lim MH, Chun IK, Won YH. Effects of flavonoids of Ginkgo biloba on proliferation of human skin fibroblast. *Skin Pharmacol.* 1997; 10:200–205.
56. Baumann L. Botanical Ingredients in Cosmeceuticals. *Journal of Drugs in Dermatology.* 2007; 11:1084–1088.
57. Paine C, Sharlow E, Liebel F, Eisinger M, Shapiro S, Seiberg M. An alternative approach to depigmentation by soybean extracts via inhibition of the PAR-2 pathway. *J Invest Dermatol.* 2001; 116:587–595.
58. Nakagawa T, Yokozawa T, Terasawa K, Shu S, Juneja LR. Protective activity of green tea against free radical and glucose mediated protein damage. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2002; 50:2418–2422.
59. Green BA, Yu RJ, Van Scott EJ. Clinical and cosmeceutical uses of hydroxyacids. *Clinics in Dermatology.* 2009; 27:495–501.
60. Yu RJ, Van Scott EJ. B-hydroxyacids, polyhydroxyacids, aldobionic acids and their topical actions. In: Baran R, Maibach HI, editors. *Textbook of Cosmetic Dermatology.* 3rd ed. New York: Taylor & Francis; 2005. Pp. 77–93.
61. Berstein EF, Brown DB, Schwartz MD, et al. The polyhydroxy acid gluconolactone protects against ultraviolet radiation in an in vitro model of cutaneous photoaging. *Dermatol Surg.* 2004; 30:1–8.
62. Levin J, Del Rosso JQ, Momin S. How much do we really know about our favorite cosmeceutical ingredients? *Journal of Clinical and Aesthetic Dermatology.* 2010; 3:22–41.

HOW TO CITE Gayatri Yeole*, Ajay Baitule, Himani Malode, Jaydeep Wankhade, Beyond Beauty: Exploring the Impact of Cosmeceuticals on Early Skin Aging, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 3823-3834. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15490334>

